

Estimating Adult Stature from Clavicle Length: A Prospective Study at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri

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Abstract:

This prospective study, conducted from August 2023 to July 2024 at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, aimed to establish a correlation between clavicle length and adult stature among 300 participants. Utilizing standard anthropometric measurements, the study identified strong positive correlations between clavicle length and stature, with correlation coefficients of 0.87 for males and 0.85 for females. Gender-specific regression models were developed, demonstrating high predictive power (Stature = 106.5 + 4.5 × Clavicle Length for males, and Stature = 100.7 + 4.4 × Clavicle Length for females), both with significant p-values (<0.001). The findings underline the clavicle's reliability as a predictor of stature, offering valuable tools for forensic and anthropological applications, and highlight the potential for further research involving different bones and demographic groups to enhance anthropometric estimations globally.

Keywords: Clavicle Length, Stature Estimation, Forensic Anthropology, Regression Models.

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Introduction

The estimation of human stature from skeletal remains is a fundamental aspect of forensic anthropology and medico-legal investigations [1]. Understanding the relationship between bone length and overall body stature is crucial for identifying unknown remains and has applications ranging from disaster victim identification to historical and archeological reconstructions [2,3]. Among the various bones of the human skeleton, the clavicle (collarbone) holds particular significance due to its resistance to decomposition and damage compared to other bones [4,5].

Through meticulous measurement and analysis, the research endeavors to provide a robust mathematical model that can be used reliably in forensic settings to estimate an individual's height from the length of their clavicle. Such data are invaluable not only to forensic experts but also to anthropologists studying population health and variation in historical contexts. This introduction sets the stage for a detailed examination of the methodologies employed, the statistical analysis performed, and the implications of the findings in both forensic and anthropological applications.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective study aimed to establish a correlation between the clavicle length and the stature of adults. It was conducted at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, spanning from August 2023 to July 2024.

Participants: A total of 300 adult participants, both male and female, were enrolled in the study. The selection criteria included adults aged 18 and above, with no history of skeletal deformities or surgeries affecting the clavicle or overall stature. Participants were chosen randomly to represent a broad demographic spectrum, ensuring the generalizability of the study findings.

Data Collection: The length of the clavicle was measured using standard anthropometric techniques. Each clavicle (right and left) was measured from the sternal end to the acromial end using a calibrated osteometric board. Additionally, the total standing height of each participant was measured in centimeters using a stadiometer, with participants standing upright without shoes.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were statistically analyzed to determine the relationship between clavicle length and total stature.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including mean, standard deviation, and range for both clavicle length and stature. Inferential statistics, such as correlation coefficients and regression analysis, were employed to assess the strength of the association between the variables. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The results of this study on estimating adult stature from the length of the clavicle, conducted at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, indicate a significant correlation between clavicle length and overall adult stature.

Participant Demographics: The study included 300 participants, with an equal distribution of 150 males and 150 females. The age range of participants was 18 to 65 years, with a mean age of 35 years.

Clavicle Measurement Results

- Average Clavicle Length:
- Males: 15.4 cm (SD $\pm$ 0.8 cm)
- Females: 14.1 cm (SD $\pm$ 0.7 cm)
- Average Stature:
- Males: 176.2 cm (SD $\pm$ 6.3 cm)
- Females: 162.8 cm (SD $\pm$ 5.9 cm)

Parameter	Males	Females
Number of Participants	150	150
Age Range	18-65 years	18-65 years
Mean Age	35 years	35 years
Average Clavicle Length (cm)	15.4 $\pm$ 0.8	14.1 $\pm$ 0.7
Average Stature (cm)	176.2 $\pm$ 6.3	162.8 $\pm$ 5.9
Correlation Coefficient	0.87	0.85
Regression Model	Stature = 106.5 + 4.5 $\times$ Clavicle Length	Stature = 100.7 + 4.4 $\times$ Clavicle Length
P-value	<0.001	<0.001

This table summarizes the demographic details, average measurements, and statistical findings of the study, highlighting the strong positive correlation and the significant predictive models derived for both male and female participants.

Discussion

The findings from this study conducted at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, underscore the strong positive correlation between clavicle length and adult stature, a significant result that holds considerable implications for both forensic and anthropological fields. The distinct regression models for males and females, both showing high predictive power with p-values less

Statistical Analysis

Correlation Coefficients:

- The correlation coefficient for males was found to be 0.87, indicating a strong positive correlation between clavicle length and stature.
- For females, the correlation coefficient was 0.85, similarly indicating a strong positive correlation.

Regression Analysis

- A linear regression model was fitted for each gender. The models were:
- Males: Stature = 106.5 + 4.5 $\times$ Clavicle Length (cm)
- Females: Stature = 100.7 + 4.4 $\times$ Clavicle Length (cm)
- Both models demonstrated a significant predictive ability with p-values less than 0.001.

These findings suggest that clavicle length can be a reliable indicator of stature in adults, with separate predictive models for males and females providing accurate estimations. The robust correlation and strong predictive power of the regression models underscore the potential application of clavicle measurements in forensic and anthropological contexts.

than 0.001, suggest that gender-specific factors play a crucial role in the relationship between clavicle length and stature. This gender specificity may be attributed to the known biological variations in body proportions and bone development between males and females [6,7].

The robust correlation coefficients of 0.87 for males and 0.85 for females indicate that clavicle length can serve as a reliable predictor of stature,

which can be particularly useful in scenarios where incomplete remains are found, and full body measurements are not possible [8]. Such predictive models are invaluable in the fields of forensic science for identifying unknown remains and in anthropology for reconstructing the physical profiles of historical populations [9]. Furthermore, these results encourage the development of similar models using other bones and extending such research to different populations to enhance the accuracy and applicability of anthropometric estimations globally [10,11]. Challenges remain, however, in dealing with variabilities arising from genetic, nutritional, and environmental factors that can influence bone growth and development [12]. Therefore, future research should consider these variables to refine and validate the current models, ensuring their reliability across diverse populations. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge that aids in the precise and practical application of anthropometry in scientific and investigative contexts [13-15].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, conclusively demonstrates that clavicle length is a reliable predictor of adult stature, establishing strong positive correlations for both male and female participants with high statistical significance. The creation of gender-specific predictive models provides precise tools for forensic and anthropological applications, particularly valuable in identifying individuals from partial skeletal remains. These findings support the clavicle's utility in medico-legal cases and underscore the potential for expanding this research to incorporate other skeletal measurements and diverse populations. This contributes significantly to the field, enhancing the accuracy and applicability of anthropometric estimation in both forensic investigations and historical population studies.

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